

Estimation of Stability Constants of Some Schiff's base Complexes with Lewis acid. A possible role of Intramolecular hydrogen bonding in these Compounds

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The composition and stability of the Aluminium complexes of some substituted salicylidene aniline Schiff bases were spectrophotometrically determined. The results indicate that these complexes were of 1:1 composition and their stability depends on the nature of substituent groups. Intramolecular hydrogen bonding was found to play an important role in the relative stabilities of these complexes.

SCHIFF base complex formation has been of great interest in recent years. Mix¹ has reported the formation of Schiff base complexes as intermediates in some biochemical reactions. Nako² has studied the stability of fused rings in metal chelate complexes of Schiff bases prepared by the reactions of salicylaldehyde and dipeptides containing glycine or β -alanine. Harris and coworkers³ have studied the complex formation of Cu(II), Ni(II), Fe(II) and Mn(II) with tetradentate salicylaldehyde Schiff bases.

In visual pigments, retinal is attached to a primary amino group associated with the visual protein (opsin). The absorption maxima of these pigments are much higher than the corresponding aldehydes. These observations aroused our curiosity to study the environmental factors that can change the absorption properties of these Schiff bases. Most of the previous work has been concerned with transition metal-Schiff base complexes. The present work was undertaken to study the various factors affecting the stability constants of complexes formed by the reaction of $AlCl_3$ and salicylidene aniline Schiff bases containing different substituents. Al^{+3} has been chosen as a representative non transition element which is known to catalyze a variety of reactions involving Schiff bases, probably through the formation of intermediate Al-Schiff base complexes. In addition $AlCl_3$ has a much better solubility in ethanol than other salt.

Experimental

Salicylidene-aniline, salicylidene-*p*-methoxyaniline, salicylidene-*p*-methylaniline, and salicylidene-*p*-bromoaniline were prepared according to the procedure described by El-Bayoumi and coworkers⁴. The molecular structure of these compounds has been established by spectroscopic methods, as illustrated in Table 1.

Aniline, *p*-toluidine, *p*-anisidine and ethanol were purified by standard methods.

TABLE 1—SPECTRAL PROPERTIES OF THE LIGANDS

Substituent (X)	M.P. (°C)	U. V. spectra in ethanol (nm.)	I. R. spectra in $CHCl_3$ (cm. ⁻¹)
H	48-50	230, 270, 238	1625
CH_3O	88-89	234, 268, 350	1627, 1601, 1485
CH_3	81-82	233, 271, 342	1624, 1110
Br	100	234, 271, 342	1620, 1600

p-Bromoaniline (BDH) was used without further purification. The ultra violet absorption spectra were recorded by Unicam SP 800 and SP 500 spectrophotometers, using 1 cm quartz cells.

Results and Discussion

In the following discussion, salicylidene-*p*-methoxyaniline complex has been chosen as a representative of the series.

The wavelength of maximum absorption of the $AlCl_3$ complexes of this Schiff base was centered at 396 nm. The absorbances of a series of solution containing a fixed amount of $AlCl_3$ solution and variable excess of Schiff base were measured at the above mentioned wavelength. The maximum absorbance was obtained by mixing 1.5 ml of 5×10^{-4} M Schiff base with 0.25 ml of $AlCl_3$, 5×10^{-4} M, i.e., when the metal: ligand molar ratio is 1:6 (Table 2)

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF METAL : LIGAND MOLAR RATIO ON ABSORBANCE USING SCHIFF BASE (II)*

ml. of 5×10^{-4} M AlCl_3	ml. of 5×10^{-4} M Schiff base	Absorbance
0.25	0.25	0.050
0.25	0.50	0.067
0.25	0.75	0.100
0.25	1.00	0.115
0.25	1.50	0.180
0.25	2.00	0.180
0.25	2.25	0.175

* Formula are given in Table 3.

dissociated. The degree of dissociation α can then be determined from the equation :

$$\alpha = (A_m - A_s)/A_m$$

If the original concentration of the complex is C, the stability constant for a 1 : 1 complex is then given by :

$$K = 1 - \alpha/\alpha^2 C$$

The concentration C is assumed to be equal to that of metal ion, since the latter reacts completely with the ligand. The average values of the apparent stability constant K and the stability periods are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—CALCULATED PARAMETERS FOR SALICYLIDENE ANILINE- AlCl_3 COMPLEXES

Ligand	λ_{max} for complex (nm)	Metal/ligand molar ratio for max. absorbance	Stability period (min)	Apparent stability constant K^*
	(I) 396	1 : 4	1.5	0.386×10^4
	(II) 396	1 : 6	3.0	2.150×10^4
	(III) 390	1 : 6	3.0	1.410×10^4
	(IV) 401	1 : 6	1.0	0.271×10^4

 K^* = Average of three readings.

The stability period of this complex was obtained by measuring the absorbance of the solution of maximum absorbance as a function of time at 396 nm. The time interval during which the colour was stable was found to be three minutes.

The composition of these complexes has been determined by three different methods, namely the continuous variation method by Job⁵, the mole ratio method⁶ and the slope ratio method⁷. The result indicated that all the complexes were of 1 : 1 type.

The apparent stability constants were determined by the method of Harvey and Manning⁷. This method involves the measurement of the absorbance, A_s , of a solution containing stoichiometric amounts of metal and ligand, and is considered to be highly dissociated. The absorbance A_m of another solution containing the metal and a large excess of the ligand is also determined. This solution is assumed to be only very slightly

It is observed from these results that the stability constants of this series are a function of the substituent present on the aniline ring. The value is decreasing in the order of :

This variation could be due to the decreasing inductive effect of the substituent. The more the electron donating power of the group is, the higher would be the electron density around the nitrogen, which results in greater stability. These results clearly indicate the dependence of the stability constants of these complexes on the electron density on the nitrogen atom.

The stability constants of benzylidene aniline series with the same substituents were examined previously⁸. The values of these constants for this series were found to be much higher than the values obtained for the salicylidene series. Present studies showed the effect of

the *o*-hydroxyl group in decreasing the value of stability constant. This effect at the first glance was unexpected since the hydroxyl group is an electron donating group.

Charette and his coworkers⁹, observed that a Schiff base of *N*-salicylidene-2-aminopropane exists chiefly in the form of intramolecular hydrogen bonding as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1

Such a hydrogen bonded six membered ring may also exist in salicylidene aniline series. This hydrogen bond formation may result in decreased electron density around nitrogen, thus giving rise to a lower value of stability constants. Model building of such a compound support H-bonding without any increase in the steric hindrance in the molecule. However, the possibility of decreased stability by steric hindrance is not excluded.

Salicylidene-*p*-bromoaniline has a stability constant value of 0.271×10^4 , while the value of benzylidene-*p*-bromoaniline could not be obtained experimentally, because of the possible fast dissociation of the complex. The possible reason for these results could be the competition between the ortho hydroxyl group for hydrogen bond formation with the unpaired electrons of nitrogen, and the electron withdrawing ability of bromine, thus making the electron density around the nitrogen less

available for bromine. This could also result in a decreased conjugation of the unpaired electrons of nitrogen with the pi-electrons of the phenyl ring. On the other hand, in benzylidene-*p*-bromoaniline, the electrons around the nitrogen are in full conjugation with the phenyl ring, and consequently to the electron withdrawing effect of the bromine resulting in an unmeasurable stability constant value.

Conclusion

The stability constant values of the salicylidene aniline complexes with AlCl_3 were found to depend upon electron density around the nitrogen atom. The increased electron density is due to the increased electron donating power of the substituents. *o*-Hydroxyl group was found to play an important role in hydrogen bond formation, resulting in a decrease electron density around the nitrogen and less conjugation of the unpaired electron with the phenyl ring, causing a lower value in the stability constants.

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